

MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH

Butunbayeva Aziza Sayfullo qizi

Tashkent State Institute of Stomatology,
Assistant teacher

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ABSTRACT

Modern educational development has given rise to a new direction of innovative pedagogy. Innovative means "introduction (dissemination) of innovation". The socio-psychological aspect of innovation was developed by the American researcher E. Rogers. He studied the classification of the participants of the innovation process, their attitude to the innovation, etc. The concepts of novelty and innovation are mutually different in scientific directions. "Innovation" means a tool, new method, methodology, technology. "Innovation" is a process that develops according to certain stages of education.

The development of world science is growing and developing day by day. It was this positive development that had an impact on our country. Advanced innovative technologies are being applied to our world of science. It would not be wrong to say that the wide application of advanced, modern innovative technologies in the fields of education has opened the door to many opportunities and goals for young people learning foreign languages. Language learning is one of the most important areas in human society. Language, which is a means of communication, can be acquired practically in a natural environment, i.e. in the family, among the public or in an organized manner. Knowledge of language phenomena is taught theoretically. Knowledge of languages, especially multilingualism, is of great importance in our time when international relations are on the rise. Pupils and students studying in our country usually study three languages. These languages are referred to by special names. These are: L1, second language, and foreign language. The L1 is the first language that plays a special role in the formation of thinking. When talking about the second language, it is considered as the language of relatives and neighbors consisting of representatives of other nationalities (Jalolov, 2012).

The methodology of foreign language teaching as a science has more than 200 years of history. During this period, it can be observed that different attitudes towards foreign language teaching methods were expressed. Academician L.V. Shcherba belongs to one of these views. In his opinion, the methodology of teaching any subject is not considered a theoretical subject depending on whether it is a subject. It solves practical problems (Shcherba, 1974). In particular, the methodology of foreign language teaching does not rely only on psychologists, it is based on general and specific linguistics. If linguistics deals with

the origin of the language and the movements of the movement, the methodology answers the question of what to do in order to actually load the necessary language phenomenon as the basis for these physical exercises.

The most valuable books on methodology are also written by linguists. These include G. Suit, one of the 19th century phoneticians and a great English linguist, O. Yespersen, who was considered the most original phonetician and theoretical linguist in England at the end of the 19th and early 20th centuries, and one of the most prominent French linguists of the late 19th and early 20th centuries, F. Bryuns and Brealya, prominent anglicist and famous phonetician V. Fyotor and others. Academician L.V. Shcherba and his mentor, the great linguist scientist I.A. Baudouin-de-Courtone and their students dealt with the issue of language teaching methodology in Russia. Psychologists had a different attitude to the methodology of foreign language teaching. Professor V.A. Artemov expressed a valuable opinion about the mutual relations of methodology and psychology. In his opinion, psychology provides material for methodology. Methodology studies how a teacher conducts a lesson. Psychology deals with how students learn this subject. However, one cannot fully agree with this opinion. Because the teacher in the process of teaching, and the student in the period of mastering, experience certain mental processes and situations, whether they want to or not, they face the laws of psychology and are affected by them (Saydaliyev, 2004).

The history of methods in our country was thoroughly studied by the famous methodist professor I.V. Rakhmanov. The translation method is mainly in two forms, called grammar-translation and text-translation methods. From the point of view of the grammar-translation method, a foreign language is studied for general educational purposes. Grammatical exercises are performed in order to develop the logical thinking of the language learner. Grammatical knowledge is considered the main goal of education. The main principles of this method are as follows:

1. Language learning is based on written speech.
2. Grammar was taken as the subject of study, and vocabulary was chosen accordingly. Grammatical exercises were the main method of work.
3. First, grammatical rules were memorized, and then it was recommended to make sentences based on the rules.
4. Grammatical forms and the meaning of words are revealed by means of word-for-word translation.
5. The language material is mastered by means of word-for-word translation and dry memorization.
6. Limited to individual memorization of words out of context (Rahmanov, 1975).

Method without translation. Various forms of this method are known historically. They can be divided into two large groups: natural and correct methods. Learning a foreign language in a natural way should be similar to the conditions of mastering the mother tongue. The idea that the main goal of the method is to create an opportunity to learn to read and write by learning to speak a foreign language is formed as a practical goal. The most important of the principles included in the natural method is to create an ideal environment. Various approaches have appeared in the practical application of the advanced methodical principles. This can be clearly seen in the creative activity of the method exponents.

The new interpretation of the goal of foreign language education was mainly based on

the results of pragmatic linguistics research. This branch of linguistics interprets language not as a system of linguistic forms, but as a field of human activity. The method of "Communicative didactics" is also considered important in the methodology of foreign language teaching. Communicative didactics includes the following.

- Open and flexible lesson concept;
- Subject and content are important;
- The main form of work in the lesson is conversation and group work;
- To activate students and to use the language creatively and freely it is necessary to pay attention;
- Strong training based on the principle of understanding to express thoughts pay attention;
- In revealing the meaning, determining the scope of action and organizing the exercise visualization (visual support) plays an important role;
- Studying daily speech communication in a real life situation (dialogue practice);
- Verbal use of the language and at the same time original texts understanding is important (Neuner, 2005).

Communicative didactics prioritizes the use of natural speech situations as a material for listening comprehension, that is, you can give examples of announcements in transport, stations, advertisements on radio and television, conversations on the phone, etc.

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